

Committed to protect citizens from hazardous chemicals

HYPIEND

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The HYPIEND project investigates the effects of multiple Endocrine Disrupting Chemicals (EDCs) exposure on the function and epigenetic programming of the hypothalamus-pituitary axis.

The main goal is to delineate interventional strategies for minimizing its exposure and consequences on the neuroendocrine system during the perinatal and pre-pubertal stages.

HYPIEND

Understanding and preventing the impact of endocrine disruptors in sensitive populations

One of the first research projects to study Endocrine Disrupting Chemicals' (EDC) effects on the hypothalamus-pituitary axis using a multidisciplinary approach, including preclinical models and two European-wide clinical studies.

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HYPIEND is one of the first projects to study EDCs exposure and effects on the hypothalamus-pituitary axis using a **multidisciplinary approach**:

Computational data analysis to identify coexposure patterns

Laboratory studies on effects of EDCs exposure in HP axis

Intervention studies in pregnancy, breastfeeding and childhood

The project findings will be used to:

1. Delineate interventional strategies
2. Improve public health
3. Raise consumer awareness on EDCs impacts
4. Protect ecosystems and wildlife
5. Shape government regulations and policies

HYPIEND project will conduct two lifestyle intervention studies

The project will conduct two European-wide clinical studies in pregnant women, their infants, and pre-pubertal children to minimize exposure to EDCs.

1 In **pregnant and breastfeeding women**, and their **offspring** up to 18 months

Spain, Belgium and Poland

810 pregnant women and their infants

2 In **children** aged 6-8 years old, **parents**, and **schools**

Spain and Belgium

700 prepubertal 6-8 children and their parents

The studies will use...

Behavioural change app

Educational workshops

School educational programme

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Endocrine Disrupting Chemicals (EDCs) are chemicals that can **interfere with the endocrine system, particularly during developmental stages of life.**

In 2022, the EU Commission proposed new hazard classes under its chemicals regulation, including endocrine disruption.

Where can EDCs be found?

- Pesticides
- Clothing, furniture, paints, electronics
- Food and drinking
- Food contact materials
- Plastics and plasticizers
- Personal care products
- Household cleaning products
- Children products (e.g. toys)
- Industrial chemicals